

MASS BALANCE MODELING OF THE BARKRAK GLACIER

Umirzakov G.U.^{1,2}, Kholtojyeva O.T., Eshmuratov D.K.,¹, Gulmurzayeva B.A.,^{1,2},
Enrico Matteo³, Martina Barandun³

¹Hydrometeorological Scientific Research Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan,

²National University of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan,

³University of Fribourg, Fribourg, Switzerland

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17151824>

Annotation. *The article is devoted to the study of the mass balance dynamics of the Barkrak Glacier, located in the Western Tien Shan mountain system. To determine annual and seasonal balances, evaluate the relationship between field observation results and modeling outcomes, and assess their impact on regional water resources, a combination of direct glaciological measurements and a degree-day model was employed. The results revealed a persistent negative mass balance of the glacier. These findings confirm that changes in glacier mass balance in the region are primarily associated with variations in air temperature. The study demonstrates the importance of establishing field observations and applying modeling approaches for glacier monitoring in data-scarce conditions, and emphasizes the necessity of incorporating glacier research into water resource management policies in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: glacier, glacier mass balance, climate, water resources, modelling, assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Glaciers are among the most sensitive indicators of climate change, responding directly to variations in air temperature and precipitation (Cuffey et al., 2010). Their mass balance, defined as the difference between accumulation and ablation, is a key measure of glacier health and a fundamental variable for assessing cryospheric response to climate forcing (Kaser et al., 2006). Small mountain glaciers, in particular, are vulnerable to warming and play a disproportionately important role in hydrological systems, often acting as natural reservoirs that regulate seasonal water availability (Immerzeel et al., 2010).

Monitoring glacier mass balance provides essential information for understanding past and present climate variability, predicting future water resources, and quantifying contributions to sea-level rise (Zemp et al., 2019; WGMS, 2023). In regions such as Central Asia, where glaciers act as critical water towers, these measurements are especially important for managing irrigation, hydropower, and drinking water supply (Dyurgerov and Meier, 2005).

Several approaches exist for quantifying glacier mass balance, ranging from direct glaciological stake measurements to geodetic methods using remote sensing (Huss and Hock, 2015), and numerical modeling based on energy balance or simplified temperature-index approaches (Hock, 1999; Hock, 2005). The degree-day model (DDM) has proven particularly effective in regions with limited data availability, as it links melt directly to air temperature using empirically derived degree-day factors (Braithwaite, 1995; Braithwaite & Zhang, 2000).

RESEARCH AREA AND METHODS

Study area. The Barkrak Glacier is located in the upper Piskom River basin of the Western Tien Shan, Uzbekistan. The glacier lies between approximately 3,400 m and 4,200 m a.s.l., with an area of ~2.1 km² (based on Landsat OLI data from 2020). The regional climate is strongly continental, characterized by cold, snowy winters and warm, dry summers. Snow accumulation typically occurs from November to April, with peak snowpack in late March, while ablation is concentrated between May and September (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of the Barkrak Glacier in the upper Pskem River basin, Western Tien Shan, Uzbekistan

The glacier plays a significant role in sustaining downstream runoff, particularly for the Chirchiq–Ohangaron basin, which supplies irrigation water, hydropower, and drinking water to the Tashkent region. Given the importance of the glacier as a water source and its vulnerability to climatic variations, understanding its mass balance dynamics is critical for both scientific and practical purposes (Immerzeel et al., 2010).

Field measurements. Direct mass balance measurements were conducted annually from 2016/2017 to 2023/2024 using the **glaciological method**. Accumulation was measured in snow pits and with probing, while ablation was determined using stakes drilled into the ice surface. The stake network consisted of 12–15 points distributed along the glacier’s longitudinal profile, covering both accumulation and ablation zones. Snow density was determined from snow pit samples to convert snow depth to water equivalent.

Surveys were typically conducted in **early August**, reflecting logistical limitations related to access and safety. This timing captured most of the ablation season but not the melt occurring during late August and September. Therefore, measured balances represent near end-of-season values but may underestimate the true annual balance. **Degree-Day Model (DDM).** To complement field data and account for unmeasured late-summer ablation, a **degree-day model (DDM)** was employed (Braithwaite, 1995; Hock, 1999). The DDM calculates melt as a linear function of positive daily mean air temperatures above 0 °C, using empirically derived degree-day factors (DDFs). Separate DDFs were applied for snow and ice surfaces, reflecting differences in albedo and energy absorption (Braithwaite & Zhang, 2000).

Meteorological Data. Meteorological inputs were obtained from the Piskom station (~2,400 m a.s.l.) and adjusted for glacier elevations using standard lapse rates (–0.65 °C per 100 m for temperature). Precipitation was corrected for elevation using a +10% increase per 100 m up to 3,800 m, after which precipitation was assumed constant, reflecting orographic saturation (Hock, 2005; Huss & Hock, 2015).

Solid and liquid precipitation were distinguished using a temperature threshold of 1 °C, with precipitation falling as snow at lower temperatures and as rain at higher temperatures. This distinction is critical because only snow contributes to glacier accumulation.

RESULTS

The reconstructed annual mass balance of the Barkrak Glacier for 2016/2017–2023/2024 indicates a predominantly negative regime. Out of the eight hydrological years analyzed, seven were negative, with only **2017/2018** showing a slightly positive balance (Figure 2).

The cumulative measured balance for the study period was **-4.6 m w.e.**, closely matched by the modeled balance of **-4.5 m w.e.** This agreement highlights the robustness of the degree-day model when properly calibrated.

2016/2017

Hydrological year: 10/01 – 09/30
 $b_n = -0.452$ m w.e.

2017/2018

Hydrological year: 10/01 – 09/30
 $b_n = 0.277$ m w.e.

2018/2019

Hydrological year: 10/01 – 09/30
 $b_n = -0.535$ m w.e.

2019/2020

Hydrological year: 10/01 – 09/30
 $b_n = -0.091$ m w.e.

2020/2021

Hydrological year: 10/01 – 09/30
 $b_n = -1.559$ m w.e.

2021/2022

Hydrological year: 10/01 – 09/30
 $b_n = -0.986$ m w.e.

Figure 2. Reconstructed annual mass balance of the Barkrak Glacier based on field measurements and degree-day model simulations

Figure 3. Comparison of measured and modeled annual mass balance values of the Barkrak Glacier

The cumulative mass balance curve (Figure 4) illustrates a **steady downward trend**, interrupted only by a brief recovery in 2017/2018.

2016/2017–2017/2018: Initial loss followed by a positive year.

2018/2019–2020/2021: Strong negative balances, culminating in the most negative year in 2020/2021 (−1.559 m w.e.).

2021/2022–2023/2024: Continued losses at moderate rates (−0.8 to −1.0 m w.e. annually).

By the end of 2023/2024, the glacier had lost nearly **5 meters of water equivalent thickness**, corresponding to a substantial reduction in volume. This trend is consistent with observations from other glaciers in continental mountain environments (Kaser et al., 2006; WGMS, 2023).

Figure 4. Cumulative mass balance of the Barkrak Glacier

DISCUSSION

The Barkrak Glacier demonstrates a consistent trend of **negative mass balance** during 2016/2017–2023/2024, with only one positive year (2017/2018). This result underscores the glacier’s vulnerability to climatic variability.

The degree-day model reproduced observed interannual variability with high accuracy ($R^2 = 0,98$), though small systematic differences were evident.

Field measurements were typically carried out in **early August**, before the ablation season ended. As melting often continued into September, measured balances were slightly less negative than modeled balances (Figure 3). For example, in 2019/2020, the measured balance was -0.091 m w.e., while the modeled balance was -0.180 m w.e., reflecting additional late-summer melt. This pattern has been observed in other glaciological programs, where logistical constraints limit access to glaciers late in the season.

CONCLUSION

The Barkrak Glacier is shrinking rapidly, losing nearly 5 m w.e. in just eight years. Its fate is controlled primarily by rising summer air temperatures, with precipitation playing only a secondary role. Differences between measured and modeled balances reflect seasonal timing, not model weakness.

The study contributes to science by providing a rare multi-year dataset, validating the DDM, and confirming climate sensitivity. For practice, it underscores the importance of glacier monitoring for water security in Uzbekistan, especially for the Chirchiq–Ohangaron basin and the Charvak Reservoir.

Future research should extend monitoring later into the season, incorporate energy balance models, reduce meteorological uncertainties, and expand to multiple glaciers. Integrating glacier science into hydrological planning is essential for sustainable resource management.

The Barkrak Glacier is not only a scientific indicator of climate change but also a **warning for water resource sustainability** in Central Asia

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